

Preconcentration and Separation of Gold(III) and Silver(I) from each other and from Base Metals using a Chelating Ion-exchanger containing Quinaldinic Acid Amide Grouping

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The synthesis of a chelating resin, styrene divinylbenzene based quinaldinic acid amide resin as well as the sorption and desorption characteristics of gold(III), silver(I) and other ten metal ions have been described. This chelating resin is highly selective for Au^{III} and Ag^I. The maximum sorption capacity of this resin for Au^{III} is 3.98 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 1.0 while that for Ag^I is 0.68 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 7.6. The resin exhibits no affinity for the alkali and alkaline earth metals. The moderate equilibration rate makes it suitable for column work. Recovery to the extent of 99.5% of Au^{III} and of 99.9% of Ag^I has been possible using thiourea in HClO₄ and 3 N HNO₃, or 5% KCN respectively. Using this resin, Au^{III} and Ag^I were quantitatively separated from each other and from other base metals. This resin has been successfully applied for the separation and preconcentration of gold from dust of goldsmiths' shop and mud and also for silver from rock samples.

CHELATING ion-exchangers containing various functional groups have been developed in the last two decades for preconcentration of metal ions from aqueous solutions as they exhibit selectivity towards a particular metal ion or groups of metal ions depending on the nature of the chelating group or groups. However, the number of such chelating ion-exchangers used for the preconcentration of gold(III) or silver(I) are limited¹⁻⁷. Out of these only the resins containing polyhydroxamic acid⁸, tertiary aliphatic amide⁹ or thioglycolate¹ as the functional group have been reported to possess high capacity for gold(III) or silver(I). Procedures have been developed for the recovery of these two metals from various sources containing trace amounts of them, such as, sea water, waste water of gold plating industry, brine and such other natural water using some of these chelating resins⁸⁻¹².

The present report describes the synthesis and use of a new styrene-divinylbenzene based copolymer containing quinaldinic acid amide as the chelating group. This resin has high capacity for gold(III) in acidic region and for silver(I) in the

alkaline region offering an easy method for the separation from each other. The capacity for gold(III) is comparable to polyhydroxamic acid⁸ and better than all other resins so far used. Both the metals have been separated from other metals including base metals in synthetic mixtures and natural samples.

Experimental

A Shimadzu AA-646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer and a Shimadzu 20 doublebeam spectrophotometer were used. A Sambros 335 digital pH meter was used for adjustment of pH.

Gold(III) solution was prepared by dissolving gold chloride (Johnson, Matthey) in deionised water and estimated¹³. Silver(I) solution was prepared by dissolving silver nitrate (E. Merck) in dilute nitric acid and estimated¹⁴. The stock solution of other metal ions, e.g., Na^I, K^I, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II} and Fe^{III} were prepared from their salts or oxides and estimated¹⁵.

Buffer solution: Different buffers were prepared by mixing varying proportions of sodium chloride and hydrochloric acid (pH 0.5–3.9) or acetic acid and sodium acetate (pH 3.9–5.9). Solutions of pH above 5.9 were controlled by ammonium nitrate and ammonium hydroxide. During study of silver and lead, pH was adjusted simply by sodium hydroxide and nitric acid upto pH 5.9 followed by ammonium nitrate and ammonium hydroxide for pH above 5.9. Acidity of the solution below pH 0.5 was adjusted with HCl.

Eluting agents: The eluting agents used were 2N H₂SO₄ for Na^I, K^I, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Fe^{III}; 3 N HNO₃ for Pb^{II} and Ag^I and 10% thiourea in 4 N HClO₄ for Au^{III}.

Ion-exchange column: Glass columns (1 cm dia x 15 cm) were each packed with previously swollen resin (5 g) to a height of 8 cm.

Introduction of the chelating group into the polymer matrix: Styrene-DVB polymer beads (Thermax Private Ltd., Poona, India) of 80–100 mesh size having 8% crosslinking were first nitrated using concentrated H₂SO₄ and HNO₃. The nitrated polymer was reduced to aminopolymer using tin and concentrated HCl. The amino-resin was finally condensed with quinaldinyl chloride by refluxing in toluene medium over a boiling water-bath for 24 h. Quinaldinyl chloride was prepared from quinaldinic acid and thionyl chloride following standard procedure. The final product was first washed with methanol and kept immersed in 2 N HCl for 24 h and then washed with water to make it free from chloride, dried in air and stored.

Separation of metal ions by the resin: The sorption capacity vs pH contours for different metal ions were obtained by batch equilibration of 0.5 g of resin with solutions of individual metal ions at different pH over 24 h. The resin was filtered off and washed with the buffer of same pH. The metal ions sorbed by the resin were eluted using suitable eluting agents. The amount of the metal ion sorbed by the resin as well as the unabsorbed amount were determined. Atomic absorption/ flame emission spectrophotometer¹⁸ was used to determine the concentration of Na^I, K^I, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Fe^{III}. The concentrations of Au^{III}, Pb^{II} and Ag^I were determined spectrophotometrically¹⁹. For the determination of concentration of gold(III), rhodamin B was used as colorimetric reagent and the gold–rhodamin B complex was extracted in isopropyl ether. The absorbance of the clear ether extract was measured at 570 nm. Dithizone was used as colorimetric reagent for Pb^{II} and Ag^I and extracted in carbon tetrachloride, the absorbance being measured at 520 and 460 nm respectively. Timed equilibration with the metal ion solution with appreciable capacities were studied to obtain $t_{1/2}$ of the resin for different metal ions (Table 1).

TABLE 1—TIME TAKEN FOR 50% UPTAKE OF METAL IONS BY RESIN

	Cu ^{II}	Pb ^{II}	Ag ^I	Cd ^{II}	Au ^{III}
pH of determination	4.0	4.0	7.6	5.0	1.0
$t_{1/2}$ (min)	90	80	90	108	40

Results and Discussion

Characterisation of the resin: The resin has been characterised from its ir spectra, elemental analysis, water-regain value, thermogravimetric and differential thermal analyses, stability towards common acids, alkali and γ -radiation.

The ir spectra of the resin has been studied to confirm the introduction of quinaldinic acid amide group into the polymer matrix. In addition to a sharp band at 1 500 cm⁻¹, four ring breathing bands as found in quinaldinic acid have also been identified in the final product. The nitrogen content of the nitrated polymer is 11.31%. The aminated polymer contains 11.46% nitrogen. The nitrogen present as amino group has been determined by titration in non-aqueous medium²⁰. An accurately weighed amount of the amino resin was mixed with a standardised solution of perchloric acid in glacial acetic acid, placed in air oven at 100° for 72 h and titrated with sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid using crystal violet as indicator. The value is 6.9%, which indicates about 68% conversion of the nitro group to amino group. The nitrogen content of the final chelating resin has been found to be 9.26%. The conversion of amino group to quinaldinic acid amide group is 85%.

Water regain value has been found to be 0.37 g g⁻¹ and TG and DT analyses showed the resin to be stable upto 260°, above which the decomposition of the functional group takes place. The resin is stable in all common acids like H₂SO₄, HNO₃, HCl and HClO₄ each of 4 N strength and in 2 N NaOH. The resin is also quite stable to γ -radiation. The range of exposure studied is 3.12–9.36 M.rad source for 24–72 h which caused no damage to the resin.

Sorption and desorption characteristics of Au^{III} Ag^I: The resin functional group has high affinity for the Au^{III} ions. It is evident from the fact that resin sorbs Au^{III} ions in appreciable amounts even from 4 N HCl solution. The sorption is maximum at pH 1.0 and then gradually decreases to a negligible value at pH 7.0. The sorption of Ag^I by the resin commences at pH 3.0, becomes maximum at pH 7.6 and is perceptible even at pH ~ 10.0. The pH of Ag^I solutions has been raised above 5.9 by NH₄NO₃–NH₄OH mixture as the amino complex is stable. The resin functional group–silver complex is stronger below pH 10.0 than silver–amine complex as the resin shows appreciable sorption capacity upto pH 10.0. Au^{III} is strongly bound to the resin and recovery is not possible with common acids (4 N) or even with 10% KCN solution. Other eluting agents which have been tried for Au^{III} are 10% NaCl, 10% thiourea in HCl (1–4 N) and HClO₄ (1–4 N). However, over 99% recovery of Au^{III} has been possible with 10% thiourea in 4 N HClO₄. Desorption of Ag^I was 99.9% with 3 N HNO₃ and with 5% (w/v) potassium cyanide solution. The effect of volume of eluent on elution of 5 mg of Au^{III} or Ag^I sorbed on the column has been presented in Fig. 1.

Sorption capacity and separation: Gold(III) and silver(I) have been separated from each other and also from other metal ions like Na^I, K^I, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II} and Fe^{III}. The plots of sorption capacity vs pH contour (Fig. 2) show that the maximum sorption capacity of the resin for gold(III) is 3.98 mmol g⁻¹ at pH 1.0 and for

Fig. 1. Effects of eluents: (I) elution of Ag^{I} with 3 N HNO_3 , and (II) elution of Au^{III} with 10% thiourea in 4 N HClO_4 .

Fig. 2. Sorption patterns of metal ions vs pH.

silver(I) 0.68 mmol g^{-1} at pH 7.6. Hence separation of Au^{III} and Ag^{I} has been carried out at pH 1.0. Synthetic mixtures of Au^{III} and Ag^{I} have been adjusted to pH 1.0 with HNO_3 and allowed to percolate through the column at a flow rate of $0.5-1.0 \text{ ml min}^{-1}$, when only Au^{III} is sorbed by the resin and Ag^{I} passes out unadsorbed. The sorbed Au^{III} is eluted with 10% thiourea in 4 N HClO_4 .

Au^{III} has also been separated from Na^{I} , K^{I} , Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pb^{II} and Fe^{III} around pH 1.0, as none of these metal ions get sorbed by the resin at the working pH. Au^{III} may be eluted as before. Separation of Ag^{I} from Na^{I} , K^{I} , Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pb^{II} and Fe^{III} has been effected at pH 7.6 as only Ag^{I} is sorbed at

this pH. Hydrolysis of Fe^{III} may be prevented by adding fluoride. Separation of Ag^{I} from Pb^{II} has been done at pH 5.0. In this case, Pb^{II} is also sorbed by the resin to a small extent. Ag^{I} is preferentially eluted from the resin with 5% potassium cyanide solution followed by elution of Pb^{II} with 3 N HNO_3 . The results are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF Au^{III} FROM VARIOUS METAL IONS

Metal ions	Amount taken μg	Au^{III} recovered μg	Average recovery (%)
Na^{I}	150, 300, 450	50.0, 49.0, 49.0	96.7
K^{I}	200, 300, 400	50.0, 50.0, 50.0	98.0
Ca^{II}	250, 350, 450	50.0, 49.0, 50.0	97.4
Mg^{II}	100, 150, 300	49.0, 50.0, 51.0	98.0
Cu^{II}	200, 400, 600	48.0, 49.0, 50.0	96.0
Zn^{II}	100, 200, 300	49.0, 48.0, 49.0	97.4
Cd^{II}	150, 300, 450	50.0, 49.0, 48.0	96.0
Ni^{II}	150, 300, 450	51.0, 50.0, 51.0	99.3
Pb^{II}	250, 500, 750	50.0, 49.0, 48.0	96.0
Fe^{III}	200, 500, 700	50.0, 48.0, 50.0	96.7
Ag^{I}	85, 170, 255	50.0, 50.0, 51.0	98.7

TABLE 3—SEPARATION OF Ag^{I} FROM VARIOUS METAL IONS

Metal ions	Amount taken μg	Ag^{I} recovered μg	Average recovery (%)
Na^{I}	50, 100, 150	85.0, 84.0, 83.0	98.8
K^{I}	100, 200, 300	84.0, 85.0, 81.0	98.0
Ca^{II}	100, 200, 300	84.0, 83.0, 82.0	97.6
Mg^{II}	60, 120, 180	84.0, 83.0, 82.0	97.6
Cu^{II}	120, 240, 360	81.0, 82.0, 84.0	96.8
Zn^{II}	100, 200, 300	85.0, 84.0, 83.0	98.8
Cd^{II}	150, 300, 450	84.0, 85.0, 82.0	98.4
Ni^{II}	140, 280, 420	84.0, 83.0, 82.0	97.6
Pb^{II}	400, 600, 800	83.0, 82.0, 81.0	96.6
Fe^{III}	120, 240, 360	85.0, 84.0, 85.0	99.6

*At pH 5.0.

Applications: Trace quantities of gold and silver present in different samples, e.g., dust, mud and rock were preconcentrated by column chromatography using this chelating resin. The mud and rock samples were collected from Geological Survey of India and analysed. The results have been checked with the reported values. The dust samples from goldsmiths' workshop collected from Bowbazar, Calcutta, were subjected to preconcentration and separation from other elements using the chelating resin. The values have been confirmed by the method of standard addition.

Determination of gold present in street dust: Dust samples were collected from street around workshops of goldsmiths from Bowbazar, Calcutta. The dust sample was washed with water in agitating pans and divided into two parts. The gold being much heavier was concentrated in the bottom (Part-I), the lighter portion (Part-II) was separated from Part-I. Both the parts were treated separately

TABLE 4—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF Au AND Ag FROM DUST, ROCK AND MUD

Sample	Sample taken g	Au found* μg	Concn. of Au ppm	Reported value ppm	Ag found* μg	Concn. of Ag ppm	Reported value ppm
Dust Part-I	50	1.85	0.027	—	—	—	—
Dust Part-II	50	0.80	0.006	—	—	—	—
Rock-I	1.1	—	—	—	225.5	205	217
Rock-II	0.5	—	—	—	104.0	208	225
Mud	2.7	11.84	4.2	5.4	—	—	—

*Mean of triplicate determinations.

with boiling HNO_3 (1:1). Silver present was separated and concentrated from this nitric acid solution. The dust remaining after nitric acid treatment was treated with aqua regia. Gold present was analysed in this part.

Separation and preconcentration of silver : The nitric acid extract of the street dust was analysed and it was found contain iron as the major constituent to the extent of about 6%. Quinaldine acid amide group containing chelating resin is not selective for Fe^{III} at pH above 2.0. Hydrolysis of Fe^{III} was prevented with 1.0 M citrate (25 ml). The mixture was percolated through the column around pH 7.0 when Ag^I was preferentially sorbed. Ag^I was recovered by elution with 3 N HNO_3 .

Preconcentration of gold : Iron was also found in the aqua regia extract of the dust. The resin showed affinity for gold in the acidic range hence separation of gold from iron as well as other metals was easy. The solution was made 1 N acidic and passed through the resin column when only Au^{III} was sorbed. Au^{III} was subsequently eluted with 10% thiourea in 4 N HClO_4 .

Separation and preconcentration of silver from rock samples : The rock samples of Rajpura and Machiamagra locality were digested with nitric acid (1:1). The solution was adjusted to pH 7.6 and the hydrolysis of iron present in small amounts was prevented by citrate. The solution was passed through the column when only Ag^I was sorbed, which was eluted with 3 N HNO_3 as before.

Separation and preconcentration of gold from mud samples : Mud samples of Tamax area, Bihar were digested with aqua regia. The solution was adjusted to pH 1.0 and passed through the column. Au^{III} sorbed was eluted as before. Results of these separations are presented in Table 4.

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